

2x2 Matrix Model and the Schrodinger Equation

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In a series of notes [2]-[9], it was shown that a 2x2 matrix energy eigenvalue equation is naturally contained in Einstein's 1905 energy momentum equation $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ (1). This equation, which appears to be related to the Dirac equation, but contains no spatial features, is linear in energy and describes bouncing of a particle back and forth with an overall average motion of v to the right. It appears to be quantum mechanical in nature as the energy matrix acts as an evolution operator, expectation values of operators are taken and one has an energy eigenvector representing the square roots of probability. Knuth [18] has used a model which yields directly probabilities for a particle bouncing back and forth with an average v to the right. In [2]-[9], it was shown that these probabilities, the squares of the terms of the energy eigenvector, can be obtained by maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to the constraint the $f_1 - f_2 = v$, where f_1 is the probability to move forward and f_2 , that to move backward.

In this note, we try to find a link between the 2x2 matrix equation and the Schrodinger (or Dirac) equation in a region with a potential $V(r)$. The Schrodinger equation, unlike the matrix equation, is spatial. Next, we try to see if there are any features of zitterbewegung that might apply in this case. In the 2x2 matrix model, Schrodinger's zitterbewegung can be derived [1], so it seems reasonable to ask whether there might be zitterbewegung in the more complicated case of a bound state in a potential. Finally, we raise the issue of a possible link between the Schrodinger equation and statistical mechanics. In the 2x2 model, the forward and backward postulated motion of a particle was connected to maximum entropy. It would be interesting if a similar idea could be applied to bound states. We do not present any calculations related to such entropy maximization, but mention work in the literature in which Tsallis entropy is maximized subject to constraints to obtain the ground state wavefunction without solving the single particle temperature=0 Schrodinger equation.

2x2 Matrix Model and the Schrodinger Equation

In the 2x2 model, the operator $\exp(-iHt)$, where H is the 2x2 energy matrix:

$\begin{pmatrix} p & m \\ m & -p \end{pmatrix}$ is an evolution operator. H together with the identity matrix convert an arbitrary two vector into the energy eigenvector.

If one has an energy eigenvector, then $\exp(-iHt)$ yields $\exp(-iEt)$, where E is the particle energy given in (1). It was also shown that such a particle has zitterbewegung or that $V(t) = \exp(iHt) V \exp(-iHt)$ where V , the velocity matrix is $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$.

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This zitterbewegung yields $V(t)$ as a sum of matrices with periodic coefficients of $\cos(Et)$ and $\sin(Et)$ suggesting a kind of physical periodic motion if one accepts zitterbewegung as physical. It has been suggested that spin and the wavelength of the particle are due to this zitterbewegung. A question arises as to how to extend a 2×2 matrix model to include a spatial description including the wavelength created by zitterbewegung. One possible way might be to map the energy eigenvector of the particle bouncing backward and forward (but moving on average with v in the positive direction) to $\exp(ikx)$. This would extend the time evolution operator $\exp(-iHt)$ in a relativistically invariant way. In such a case, one might be able to use conservation of energy to obtain the Schrodinger equation, with the Laplacian being used to obtain $\hbar k$, the momentum, from $\exp(ikx)$. This type of equation would keep intact the idea of the square root of probability introduced through the 2×2 matrix model. It would also allow for interference of "waves" which arise from zitterbewegung which exists in the 2×2 matrix model.

With a potential in place, however, the problem becomes much more difficult, because one no longer has a single velocity or momentum $\exp(ikx)$. The potential allows for many velocities or momenta to be stirred up in forming a resonance solution. What is interesting is that this resonance solution can again be written as a matrix equation with different plane waves coupling to plane waves from a Fourier decomposition of the potential $V(r)$ on the left hand side. On the right hand side one has $E (a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots, a_n)$. Here E is the resonance energy and a_i is the square root of the probability for the presence of a momentum of k_i . Like in the 2×2 matrix case, the right hand side is a list of square roots of probability, but in Schrodinger case, they pertain to different momentum plane wave states. (Note: in the case of the Schrodinger equation, one can solve for the wavefunction and then decompose it using a Fourier series. In general, physics books historically have treated these Fourier terms or $\exp(ikx)$ as plane wave solutions of a Schrodinger equation with no potential and have ascribed them with physical meaning.)

For the 2×2 matrix model [2]-[9] and for the Dirac equation without a potential, zitterbewegung results can be obtained. These are based on choosing an operator V (the velocity operator) such that $V(t) = \exp(iHt) V \exp(-iHt)$ leads to terms containing $\cos(Et)$ and $\sin(Et)$ as coefficients of various matrices. The idea seems to be that there is physical periodicity in the system even though an average value of the velocity operator yields only a number. It seems that zitterbewegung should be applicable to the Schrodinger equation with its set of a_i 's. One could take as the velocity operator, for example, a matrix with an entry of k_i for momentum k_i and $-k_i$ for momentum $-k_i$. Overall, the expectation value of the momentum would be 0 as the system is not translating, but such a matrix, it seems, should lead to zitterbewegung as this matrix does not seem to commute with the Hamiltonian. It is strange, however, as the zitterbewegung, with frequency E (energy) seems to apply to the whole system. In the case of the 2×2 model or the Dirac equation, zitterbewegung was applied to spin or wavelength. In the case of the bound state, it would need to apply to a physical periodic phenomenon, not already described by the wavefunction. It is interesting to note, however, that zitterbewegung gives $\cos(Et)$ and $\sin(Et)$ terms and the bound state with energy E is said to have a frequency of E in quantum mechanics.

Statistical Aspects of 2x2 Matrix Model

The 2x2 matrix model ascribes probabilities of $.5(c+v)$ and $.5(c-v)$ to the forward and backward bouncing motions of a particle moving with an average velocity of v in the forward direction. Knuth [18] has also obtained these values. Thus, the term $-k P_n \ln(P_n)$ from Shannon's entropy is not the same for different velocities v . This is interesting because in the previous section a particle with velocity v is mapped into $\exp(ikx)$. In such a case, one loses all information of the internal entropy associated with the velocity or momentum k . Different momentum k values (or v values) carry different internal entropies and these do not seem to appear in calculations of statistical mechanics. If one took the typical Boltzmann factor $\exp(-.5m v^2/T)/C$ where C is the normalization constant it seems that the Shannon entropy contribution for a particle with v would be

$$.5(c+v)\exp(-.5m v^2/T)/C \ln\{ .5(c+v) \exp(-.5m v^2/T)/C\} + .5(c-v)\exp(-.5m v^2/T)/C \ln\{ .5(c-v) \exp(-.5m v^2/T)/C\}$$

In the nonrelativistic case, the 2x2 matrix contribution is negligible because v/c tends to 0 and so any such contribution would not have appeared in nonrelativistic experiments.

Connection with Statistical Mechanics

It was shown in [2]-[9] that the 2x2 matrix model (related to the Dirac equation) represents a probabilistic model of a particle bouncing back and forth as it moves with velocity v in the right direction. It was also shown that these probabilities could be obtained by maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to the constraint $f_1 - f_2 = v$ where f_1 is the probability to bounce to the left and f_2 to the right. Thus, in the 2x2 matrix model the two types of statistical models, namely the quantum mechanical and statistical mechanical lead to the same result. This is interesting because a priori it is not clear why there should be two independent statistical models in nature. In [23], it was suggested that a Schrodinger equation in cylindrical coordinates could be used to obtain the Boltzmann spatial density for a gas rotating in a cylinder. Plastino [26] and Casa [25] have done much work showing that ground state wavefunctions can be obtained without solving the Schrodinger equation. Instead, the Tsallis entropy is maximized subject to constraints. Thus, Plastino and Casa and others link the statistics of the single particle (Temperature = 0) Schrodinger equation to a "modified Tsallis" statistical mechanics. In other words, there do not appear to be two independent statistical models in existence in their analysis. It is interesting in such a scenario, that a variational approach to the derivation of the Schrodinger equation as a matrix (or differential equation) with the wavefunction (or eigenvector) representing square roots of probabilities is equivalent with the idea of entropy. It seems that there should be a physical phenomenon related to this "square root" of probability.

In the case of the 2x2 matrix model, the two components of the energy eigenvector representing the forward and backward bouncing motion of a particle (and being equal to the square roots of the probabilities) seem to be directly related to a physical phenomenon, namely

the bouncing. Zitterbewegung which follows from the model is directly linked to this bouncing as it is the bouncing motion which ultimately leads to the wavelength and spin. The Schrodinger equation, like the 2x2 matrix model, can also be expressed as a matrix with the Hamiltonian as the evolution operator. The square root probabilities of the eigenvector represent the weights of the "plane waves" stirred up in the system with a spatial potential. These plane waves are ultimately due to the existence of a wavelength (which can be related to the 2x2 matrix model). Thus, one would expect a physical phenomenon, related to zitterbewegung, to be associated with these weights. It does seem, as argued in the previous section, that there is zitterbewegung with the Schrodinger equation, although it is not entirely clear to what it refers. Perhaps there are a kind of periodic oscillations related to the shifting from one plane wave to another. In the case of a gas rotating in a cylinder it was argued [23] that the existence of a Schrodinger equation to solve the Boltzmann spatial density might imply that sound waves (or oscillations) were ultimately responsible for the classical spatial density which exists in the rotating gas. If such oscillations existed, then this might allow for a conceptual link between the single particle temperature=0 Schrodinger equation and ideas of entropy.

Let us consider one example related to the ground state of Schrodinger equation and the maximization of entropy. In the case of the Schrodinger equation, obtained from a variational principle, one looks for an eigenvector (of square roots of probability of plane waves) which is stationary under the operation of H, of the evolution operator $\exp(iHt)$. In such a case, the system will not change. Thus, the evolution operator is the main driver in the problem, but it should be related to physical phenomena in the system. Let us assume that one has found the ground state eigenvector. Next, consider maximizing some kind of entropy expression (Shannon's entropy Tsallis entropy etc) subject to constraints. An important question becomes what constraints to use, because there often different options. If one uses the idea that $X = \langle \text{wavefunction} | H | \text{wavefunction} \rangle = E_{\text{ground}}$ then any function can be written as an orthonormal series of the eigenfunctions of H. Then $X = \sum \{ \text{prob}(i) E_i \}$ which is larger than E_{ground} unless the function is the ground state wavefunction. Thus, it seems that the constraint X solves the problem completely and that any entropy obtained is simply consistent with the ground state wavefunction. In the approaches of Plastino and Casa [25, 26] and others, it seems that one does not solve the Schrodinger equation and that one uses simpler constraints. In such a case, one is able to maximize the entropy to find a solution.

Let us consider the 2x2 matrix in this context. It was found that one could solve the eigenvalue problem and find the square roots of the probabilities of bouncing forward and backwards. Alternatively, one could maximize Shannon's entropy subject to $f_1 - f_2 = v$, where f_1 and f_2 are the probabilities of bouncing forward and backward. If one instead uses the constraint that $\sqrt{f_1}$ and $\sqrt{f_2}$ represent the eigenvector of the energy matrix (H), then there would be no need to maximize any entropy. The constraint alone would solve the problem.

Conclusion

In this note, we have attempted to argue that the 2x2 matrix model describing a bouncing particle which moves on average with speed v in the positive direction can lead to a Schrodinger equation by mapping the bouncing particle to $\exp(ikx)$ (which compliments $\exp(-iEt)$ from the evolution operator) together with conservation of energy. It has been argued that this single particle Schrodinger equation can be written as a matrix eigenvalue equation (when the wavefunction is decomposed into plane waves (Fourier series)) which has a similar form to that of the 2x2 matrix model in that the planes waves in a potential arrange themselves so that the right hand side of the Schrodinger matrix equation is only dependent on E and the square root of the probability of each plane wave. We have also suggested that physical zitterbewegung should apply in such a case. Finally, we have discussed attempts in the literature to link the single particle (temperature =0) Schrodinger equation to Tsallis entropy so that instead of having two independent statistical models in nature, namely quantum mechanics and statistical mechanics, there is one.

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